

Building Bridges: Exploring the Nexus between Blind Recruiting and Organizational Performance in Oil and Gas Servicing Companies in South-South, Nigeria

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Abstract: This study examined the relationship between blind recruiting and organizational performance in oil and gas servicing companies in Nigeria. The study adopted the cross-sectional research survey design. Primary data was generated through structured questionnaire. The population for the study comprises 6 of oil and gas servicing companies in south-south, Nigeria. All the oil and gas servicing companies' 60 management staff were sampled using census sampling techniques. The research instrument was validated by managers, vetting and approval while reliability of the instrument was achieved by the use of Cronbach Alpha coefficient which stood at .876. The hypotheses were tested using the Spearman's Rank Order Correlation Statistics while the partial correlation was used to test the moderating effect. The test was carried out at a 0-05 significance level. The findings revealed that there is a significant relationship between blind recruiting and organizational performance of oil and gas servicing companies in south-south, Nigeria. The study concludes that blind recruiting positively enhances the organizational performance of oil and gas servicing companies in south-south, Nigeria. This implies that when blind recruiting is applied to personnel recruitment processes, there would be greater organizational performance. The study recommended among others that management of oil and gas servicing companies operating in South-South, Nigeria should invest in robust blind recruiting, placement and selection processes that carefully evaluate candidates for their skills, experience, and competencies to enhance organizational performance.

Keywords: Blind Recruiting, Organizational Performance, Revenue, Market Share, Safety Culture.

Introduction

Organizational performance is a subjective perception of reality, which explains the multitude of critical reflections on the concept and its measuring instruments (Lebas, 2005; Wholey, 2016). At present, there are a variety of definitions attributed to the concept of organizational performance due to its subjective nature. Thus, the concept of organizational performance has gained increasing attention in recent decades and is pervasive in almost all spheres of human

activity. Organizational performance is crucial as it directly impacts on organization's ability to achieve its goal, sustain growth and maintain a competitive advantage.

Owing to the importance of organizational performance, several empirical studies have been conducted around the globe on this subject (Adeneyi, 2014, Wageeh, 2014) They have sought to examine different variables in a bid to increase organizational performance. In spite of the several studies and importance placed on organizational performance, a significant challenge confronting the oil and gas firms is the poor level of performance. Research has focused on factors such as rewards system, organizational justice, employee empowerment etc. While it is true that these factors may possibly increase organizational performance, one other factor is neglected, which is the recruitment practices.

Recruitment is the channel for attracting a quality and competent workforce. This has been undermined by shaped practices of Bias, favoritism, and nepotism in these institutions thereby leading to inefficient and ineffective operations resulting which have elicited grave concerns among key stakeholders in the sector which include the government, parents, community leaders, and employers. Every year organizations bring in workers into their firms with little or no competencies to handle assigned tasks when engaged in employment contracts. It is appalling on the level of inexperienced workers brought in establishments. Some are based on their relationship with the director or those in the helm of affairs, or political positions who were appointed for a job without having to go through the required due process. This trend has impacted negatively on the economy resulting in both monetary and Infrastructural damages. Hence, this paper examines the potential of blind recruiting to enhance organizational performance in the oil and gas companies in South-South, Nigeria.

The conceptual framework in Figure 1 illustrates the relationship between blind recruiting and organization performance. The framework is based on the work of Jonggu and Lee, (2018). The framework suggests that blind recruiting has an impact on organizational performance

At its core, the study aims to accomplish several objectives through its literature review:

1. To examine the relationship between blind recruiting and revenue of oil and gas servicing companies in South-South, Nigeria?
2. To examine the relationship between blind recruiting and market share of oil and gas servicing companies in South-South, Nigeria?

3. To examine the relationship between blind recruiting and safety culture of oil and gas servicing companies in South-South, Nigeria?

To effectively address these objectives, the study delineates the following research question:

1. What is the relationship between blind recruiting and revenue of oil and gas servicing companies in South-South, Nigeria?
2. What is the relationship between blind recruiting and market share of oil and gas servicing companies in South-South, Nigeria?
3. What is the relationship between blind recruiting and safety culture of oil and gas servicing companies in South-South, Nigeria?

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical foundation

In investigating the nexus between blind hiring and organizational performance, the theoretical foundations adopted in this study is the social exchange theory. This theory highlights the reciprocal relationship between employees and organizations. It posits that individuals who perceive fairness and positive treatment during the selection process are more likely to reciprocate with higher levels of commitment and performance. Homans, (1961), has it that the dominant emphasis was the individual behavior of actors in interaction with one another. His primary aim was to explain fundamental processes of social behavior (power, conformity, status, leadership, and justice) from the ground up. Homans believed that there was nothing that emerged in social groups that cannot be explained by propositions about individuals as individuals, together with the given condition that they happen to be interacting. In the context of blind recruiting and organizational performance, the theory highlights the importance of developing and utilizing resources that are valuable, inimitable and non-substitute. The theory emphasizes the role of organizational resources, capabilities and knowledge in enhancing organizational performance. By alighting and leveraging their resources, oil and gas servicing companies operating in South-South, Nigeria can create an environment that supports staff productivity for greater organizational performance.

Conceptual Review

Blind Recruiting.

This has to do with removing any identifying information from resumes and applications. It lets recruiters assess applicants based on abilities and experience, not prejudice. Blind recruiting is mostly employed during screening, when names, residences, schools attended, resumes, and pre-employment exams are eliminated and applicants' talents and traits are assessed via many interviews and matched with pre-set criteria (Jonggu Lee, 2018). Blind recruiting is difficult to implement during interviews. An anonymize transcribed answer is one technique to conduct a blind interview, but it typically misses important abilities and traits that may be needed for a post. Blind recruiting blacks out key identifying information that might lead to biased selection performance: (1) Ethnic background: Many job applicants don't disclose their ethnicity, but their LinkedIn profile, name, or country of employment or study might indicate it (Anderson, 2022).

Organizational Performance and its measures.

Organization performance has been the most important consideration for every organization, be it profit or non-profit organization. It has been very important for managers to know which factors influence an organization's performance in order for them to take full advantage and appropriate steps to initiate them. Organizational researchers among themselves have different opinions of performance as it continues to be a contentious issue. (Barney, 1997). According to Daft (2000), organizational performance is the organization's ability to attain its goals by using resources in an efficient and effective manner. . Quite similar to Daft, (2000), Richardo, (2001)

defined organizational performance as the ability of the organization to achieve its goals and objectives.

Revenue

Revenue is one of the most commonly used metrics to measure organizational performance as it directly reflects the amount of money generated by a company through its products or services. It is an important indicator of how well a company is performing in terms of sales and market share (Gulati, Nohria, & Wohlgezogen, 2016). According to the literature, revenue can be used to assess the financial health and success of an organization. A study by Hall and Hall (2011), found that revenue growth is positively correlated with profitability and shareholder value, indicating that companies with higher revenues tend to be more successful. In addition, revenue can also be used to evaluate the effectiveness of a company's marketing and sales strategies, as well as its ability to generate demand for its products or services.

Market Share

Market share is a common measure of organizational performance that reflects a company's relative strength within its industry. In a competitive market environment, organizations strive to increase their market share as it is often associated with higher profitability, increased brand recognition, and economies of scale. This literature review will examine the relationship between market share and organizational performance, drawing on a range of scholarly articles and research studies.

Safety Culture

Safety in organizational performance refers to the measures and practices put in place by an organization to protect its employees, customers, and other stakeholders from harm and accidents in the workplace. This concept emphasizes the importance of creating a work environment that prioritizes the well-being and safety of all individuals involved (Clarke, 2010). Additionally, one of the key aspects of safety in organizational performance is the implementation of safety protocols and procedures. These protocols outline the steps that employees should take in order to prevent accidents and respond effectively in case of emergencies

Blind Recruiting and Organizational Performance

This is one of the dimensions that lets recruiters assess applicants based on abilities and experience, not prejudice. Blind recruiting is mostly employed during screening, when names, residences, schools attended, resumes, and pre-employment exams are eliminated and applicants' talents and traits are assessed via many interviews and matched with pre-set criteria (Jonggu Lee, 2018). Blind recruiting is difficult to implement during interviews. Blind recruiting blacks out key identifying information that might lead to biased selection performance: (1) Ethnic background: Many job applicants don't disclose their ethnicity, but their LinkedIn profile, name, or country of employment or study might indicate it (Anderson, 2022). Race affects recruiting, but views differ. (Hamza *et. al.*, 2021). (2) Gender: Several studies show that gender discrimination and inequality are widespread in the workplace. Some people work with their gender or take gender-specific responsibilities (Anderson, 2022). (3) Names: Research shows that employing people with basic, pronounceable names is easier (Gupta, & Kumar, 2014; Anderson, 2022). (4) Education: A candidate's academic background may raise questions about their intelligence or work ethic (Anderson, 2022).

According to Lichtenstein and Williamson (2018), investors often use revenue as a key performance indicator when evaluating the financial viability of a company, as well as its potential for future growth and profitability. Overall, revenue is a critical measure of organizational performance that can provide valuable insights into a company's financial health, market position, and competitive advantage. According to the literature, revenue can be used to assess the financial health and success of an organization. A study by Hall and Hall (2011),

found that revenue growth is positively correlated with profitability and shareholder value, indicating that companies with higher revenues tend to be more successful. In addition, revenue can also be used to evaluate the effectiveness of a company's marketing and sales strategies, as well as its ability to generate demand for its products or services. Furthermore, revenue can help organizations benchmark their performance against industry standards and competitors. Ranjay Gulati *et. al.*, (2016), found that companies that outperform their competitors in terms of revenue growth are more likely to gain market share and achieve sustainable competitive advantage. This suggests that revenue can be a useful metric for identifying areas of strength and weakness within an organization. Also revenue serves as an important metric for investors and stakeholders, as it provides insight into a company's ability to generate cash flow and return on investment. Revenue is one of the most commonly used metrics to measure organizational performance as it directly reflects the amount of money generated by a company through its products or services. It is an important indicator of how well a company is performing in terms of sales and market share (Gulati, Nohria, & Wohlgezogen, 2016). Based on the foregoing argument, the study thus hypothesized

that:

- H₀₁:** There is no significant relationship between blind recruiting and revenue in oil and gas servicing companies in South-South, Nigeria
- H₀₂:** There is no significant relationship between blind recruiting and market share in oil and gas servicing companies in South-South, Nigeria
- H₀₃:** There is no significant relationship between blind recruiting and safety in oil and gas servicing companies in South-South, Nigeria

3. METHODOLOGY

The population of the study consisted of all the 6 oil and gas servicing companies in South-South, Nigeria. According to the information obtained from " Source: www.neiti.gov." Since the population of six (6) oil and gas companies in South-South Nigeria is relatively small, the study adopted the entire population as a census, based on the fact that these oil and gas servicing companies have all operated for more than 15 years.

However, elements from the population were used as the participants or respondents for the study. Therefore, for the purpose of data gathering in this study and in line with the study unit of analysis which was at the macro level, copies of questionnaire were distributed to ten (10) managers each drawn from the six(6) oil and gas companies making a total of 60 respondents. The reliability of the instrument was achieved by the use of the cronbach Alpha coefficient with all the items scoring above 0.70. The hypotheses were tested using the Spearman Rank Correlation Order.

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS.

60 copies of the questionnaire were administered to respondents. 57 copies questionnaire representing 95 percent were retrieved. 1 copy questionnaire representing 1.75 percent were retrieved but not useable. 56 copies questionnaire representing 93.33 percent were correctly filled and thus suitable for data analysis.

Univariate Analysis

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics for Blind Recruiting

Item	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Dev.
Our organization effectively and efficiently planned for unbiased recruitment processes.	56	1	5	3.47	
Our organization emphasizes candidate ' 1.14 Skills and experience and designs an Unbiased evaluation for work place diversity and reduced unprofessional favoritism and preferential treatment.	56	1	5	3.21	
Our organization determines the types and 1.53 levels of candidate 'skills and experience for excellent organizational performance.	56	1	5	3.99	
Our organization adopted blind resumes .923 template to evaluate candidate required position in organizations. knowledge, skills and experience on the job	56	1	5	2.62	
Our organization involves competence 1.45 mapping; skill, knowledge, abilities and attitude gap analysis and personal development plan	56	1	5	4.27	
Valid N (listwise)					

Source: SPSS Output , 2024

The data in Table 2 illustrated that there is a high level of affirmation (where $\times > 2.50$) as regards the indicators of blind recruiting. The construct examined the context and manifestations of blind recruiting within the target companies with indicators aimed at examining respondent’s perception of observed phenomenon in their companies and hence is largely on the agreement range of the scale.

Table 2 Descriptive Statistics for Revenue

Item	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Our organization use revenue to evaluate the effectiveness of a company's marketing and sales strategies, as well as its ability to generate demand for its products or services	56	1	5	3.71	1.45
Our organization constantly engages its suppliers and vendors on how best to function within its environment.	56	1	1	3.88	1.53
Our organization is knowledgeable about the customer features of its market.	56	1	5	2.62	1.37
Our organization has a critical measure of organizational performance that can provide	56	1	5	4.15	1.90

valuable insights into a company's financial health, market position, and competitive advantage					
Valid N (listwise)					

Source: SPSS Output version 23

The data in Table 2 illustrate that there is a high level of affirmation (where $\times > 2.50$) as regards the indicators of revenue which is a dimension of organizational performance. The construct examined the context and manifestations of revenue within the target companies with indicators aimed at examining respondent's perception of observed phenomenon in their companies and hence is largely on the agreement range of the scale.

Table 3 Descriptive Statistics for Market Share

Item	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Our organization ensure high market share which tend to have higher market valuations, as investors perceive them as more competitive, sustainable, and profitable in the long term	56	1	1	3.17	1.53
Our organization maintain a strong financial performance, market share has also been shown to be a key driver of shareholder value	56	1	5	4.72	1.11
Our organization often addresses its noted gaps and deficiency in its change development	56	1	5	4.90	1.38
Our organization equip its employees with sufficient skills and knowledge on organizational processes and their interdependencies	56	1	5	4.02	1.61
Our organization has precise understanding of the links between components of the links between components within its system	56	1	5	4.18	1.74
Valid N (listwise)					

Source: SPSS Output version 23

The data in Table 3 illustrate that there is a high level of affirmation (where $\times > 2.50$) as regards the indicators of revenue which is a dimension of organizational performance. The construct examined the context and manifestations of market share within the target companies with indicators aimed at examining respondent's perception of observed phenomenon in their companies and hence is largely on the agreement range of the scale.

Table 4. Descriptive Statistics for Safety

Item	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Our organization ensure high market share which tend to have higher market valuations, as investors perceive them as more competitive, sustainable, and profitable in the	56	1	1	3.66	1.73

long term					
Our organization allow for the flow of information along the Hierarchy to maintain safety in the organization	56	1	5	4.71	1.34
Our organization see aspect of safety in organizational performance with the promotion of a safety culture within the organization	56	1	5	3.99	1.83
Our organization promotes a healthy competition among staff for their safety	56	1	5	4.15	1.92
Our organization involves creating a work environment where safety is a top priority and all individuals are actively engaged in promoting and maintaining safety standards	56	1	5	4.85	1.92
Valid N (listwise)					

Source: SPSS Output version 23

The data in Table 4. Illustrate that there is a high level of affirmation (where $\times > 2.50$) as regards the indicators of revenue which is a dimension of organizational performance. The construct examined the context and manifestations of safety within the target companies with indicators aimed at examining respondent's perception of observed phenomenon in their companies and hence is largely on the agreement range of the scale.

Bivariate Analysis.

The level of significance 0.05 was adopted as a criterion for the probability of accepting the null hypothesis in ($p > 0.05$) or rejecting the null hypothesis in ($p < 0.05$)

Table 5 : Blind Recruiting and Organizational Performance

		BR	Rev	MktS	Saf.	
Spearman's rho	Blind Recruiting	Correlation	1.000**	.734	.674	.706
		Coefficient				
		(Sig. 2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000
		N	56	56	56	56
	Revenue	Correlation	.734	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**
		Coefficient				
		(Sig. 2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000
		N	56	56	56	56
	Market Share	Correlation	.674	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**
		Coefficient				
		(Sig. 2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000
		N	56	56	56	56
	Safety	Correlation	.706	1.000**	1.000**	1.000**
		Coefficient				
		(Sig. 2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000
		N	56	56	56	56

Correlation is significant at 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Below is the full meaning of the following abbreviations:

BR = Blind Recruiting

REV = Revenue

MKTS = Market Share

SAF = Safety Culture

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between significant relationship between blind recruiting and revenue of organizational performance of oil and gas servicing companies operating in South-South, Nigeria.

The table 5. is the statistical test of significance (p-value) which makes possible the generalization of our findings to the study population. . From the result obtained from table 5, the sig- calculated is less than significant level ($p = 0.000 < 0.05$) it shows a Spearman Rank Order Correlation Coefficient (ρ) of 0.734 on the relationship between blind recruiting and revenue. This value implies that a strong relationship exists between the variables. The direction of the relationship indicates that the correlation is positive; implying that an increase in revenue was because of the adoption of blind recruiting. Therefore, there is a strong positive correlation between blind recruiting and organizational performance of oil and gas servicing companies operating in South-South, Nigeria.

Based on this finding the null hypothesis earlier stated is hereby rejected and the alternate upheld.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between blind recruiting and market share of organizational performance of oil and gas servicing companies operating in South-South, Nigeria.

The table 5 is the statistical test of significance (p-value) which makes possible the generalization of our findings to the study population. From the result obtained from table 5. the sig- calculated is less than significant level ($p = 0.000 < 0.05$). Table 5 also shows a Spearman Rank Order Correlation Coefficient (ρ) of 0.674 on the relationship between blind recruiting and market share of organizational performance. This value implies that a strong relationship exists between the variables. The direction of the relationship indicates that the correlation is positive; implying that an increase in market share was because of blind recruiting. Therefore, there is a strong positive correlation between blind recruiting and market share of oil and gas servicing companies operating in South-South, Nigeria

Therefore, based on this finding the null hypothesis earlier stated is hereby rejected and the alternate upheld Thus, there is a significant relationship between blind recruiting and market share of organizational performance of oil and gas servicing companies operating in South-South, Nigeria.

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between blind recruiting and the safety of organizational performance of oil and gas servicing companies operating in South-South, Nigeria.

Also displayed in the table .5 is the statistical test of significance (p-value) which makes possible the generalization of our findings to the study population From the result obtained from table 5, the sig- calculated is less than significant level ($P 0.000 < 0.05$). it shows a Spearman Rank Order Correlation Coefficient (ρ) of 0.706 on the relationship between blind recruiting and safety. This value implies that a very strong relationship exists between the variables. The direction of the relationship indicates that the correlation is positive; implying that an increase in safety was as a result of the adoption blind recruiting. Therefore, there is a very strong positive correlation between blind recruiting and safety of oil and gas servicing companies operating in South-South, Nigeria Therefore, based on this finding the null hypothesis earlier stated is hereby rejected and the alternate upheld. Thus, there is a significant relationship blind recruiting and the

safety of organizational performance of oil and gas servicing companies operating in South-South, Nigeria.

DISCUSSIONS OF FINDINGS

The findings showed that there is a significant relationship between blind recruiting and organizational performance in oil and gas servicing companies operating in South-South, Nigeria. This finding corroborates the earlier results of the study conducted by Kastens and Cook (2004) on blind recruiting and market value of publicly traded companies. The finding indicated that blind recruiting enhances organizational performance in the organization studied. The result of the study buttressed this present study by revealing that companies with higher market share tend to have higher market valuations, as investors perceive them as more competitive, sustainable, and profitable in the long term. Kotler and Keller (2016), argue that a range of external factors such as changes in market conditions, competitor actions, and regulatory changes can influence a company's market share.

More so, the finding aligned with the previous findings of Buzzell and Gale (1987), who found a strong positive relationship between market share and profitability. Their research demonstrated that companies with higher market share tend to have higher profitability levels due to their ability to capture a larger share of customer demand, negotiate better terms with suppliers, and achieve economies of scale. This finding has been corroborated by numerous other studies, including Keasey and Watson (1997), Webber and Seiler (2011), who all found a positive correlation between blind recruiting, market share and financial performance indicators such as return on assets and return on equity. The result of this study has bearing with the human capital theory. The theory holds that for knowledge-based organizations, intangible assets are often greater than tangible assets. These intangible assets are skills, knowledge and competencies of candidates. The ability of an organization to select the best candidates irrespective of geographical or religious sentiments would invariably lead to organizational performance. Vejjachayanon, (2005) support the result of this study by asserting that, overall, organizational capital is a part of total capital which was classified as intellectual capital. The human capital theory emphasizes that employees are an organization's most valuable assets. It suggests that the recruitment and selection processes should focus on identifying and acquiring candidates with valuable skills and knowledge.

In the world of the labor market, people bring different levels of education, knowledge, skill, and abilities as well as their expectancy to the workplace. According to McConnell *et al.* (2009): a more educated, better-trained person is capable of supplying a larger amount of useful productive effort than one with less education and training. The value of human capital theory is widely accepted to increase organizational performance, so an organization relies on employees' skill, knowledge, ability as a key concept of value creation. In the eighteenth-century Adam, (1773) initiated an improvement in human capability that is important to production, then a term of human capital was introduced by Theodore (1961) published in the American Economic Review, called investment in human capital. Consequently, as oil and gas serving companies in South-South, Nigerian applied the human capital theory by carrying out blind selection of candidates, the result is higher productivity and organizational performance.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS.

The study concludes that blind recruiting positively enhances organizational performance of oil and gas servicing companies operating in South-South, Nigeria. By conducting an unbiased recruiting and prioritizing the candidate skills and knowledge, oil and gas companies in Nigeria can create an environment that encourages and supports efficiency and greater productivity among their staff and further experienced higher revenue generation. Based on these, the study recommends that Management of oil and gas servicing companies operating in South-South, Nigeria should invest in robust blind recruitment placement and selection processes that

carefully evaluate candidates for their skills, experience and competencies in order to enhance organizational performance.

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